

PROBLEMS OF WOMAN AND SOCIETY IN THE NOVEL OF CHARLOTTE BRONTE

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ABSTRACT This article is devoted to the problems of women and society in the novels of Charlotte Bronte. Since Charlotte Brontë's attention to gender in her novels is a great opportunity to get a better look at the life of a woman in Victorian times. Upper and middle class women were usually separated from the commercial and intellectual world. Women's mindset and role in society at large was of considerable interest to Charlotte Brontë, as she herself was a woman striving to transcend the limitations of her era. Brontë, however, was a courageous woman who was not afraid to address the "Women's Question" in her writing, and she did it so masterfully that her novels are still the epitome of female power and ability.

Key words: women's problems, female power, society, gender problems, woman's life, turn, pay attention, intellectual world.

SHARLOTTA BRONTE ASARLARIDA AYOL VA JAMIYAT MASALALARI

ANNOTATSIYA Ushbu maqola Sharlotta Bronte romanlaridagi ayollar va jamiyat muammolariga bag'ishlangan. Sharlotta Bronte o'z romanlarida gender masalalariga katta e'tibor berganligi sababli, Viktoriya davridagi ayollarning hayotini yaxshiroq ko'rib chiqish qulay. Yuqori va o'rta sinf ayollari odatda tijorat va intellektual dunyodan ajralib turardi. Ayollarning fikrlash doirasi va umuman jamiyatdagi roli Sharlotta Bronte uchun katta qiziqish uyg'otdi, chunki uning o'zi ham o'z davrining cheklovlarini engib o'tishni istagan ayol edi. Biroq, Bronte o'z asarlarida "Ayol savoli" ga murojaat qilishdan qo'rqmaydigan jasur ayol edi va u

buni shu qadar mohirlik bilan bajarganki, uning romanlarida hozirgi kungacha ayol kuchi va qobiliyatini ifodalaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: ayol masalalari, ayol kuchi, jamiyat, gender muammolari, ayol hayoti, hal qilish, e'tibor berish, intellektual dunyo.

Introduction

The development of literature, art and culture is an important factor in raising the spirituality of people. In our country, great attention is being paid to the development of culture, art and literature, as well as mass media, along with all sectors and industries. [1] In other words, literature is a mirror of life, so it accurately reflects people's reality, dreams, attitudes, etc. It's not about words and thoughts. It has to do with human life. Literary works, at their best, provide a unique blueprint of human society. From the writings of ancient civilizations such as Egypt and China to Greek philosophy and poetry, from the epics of Homer to the dramas of William Shakespeare, from Jane Austen and Charlotte Brontë to Maya Angelou, works of literature provide insight and context for societies around the world. The Victorian era was a time of great social and political reform, especially regarding the role of women.

Women began to actively seek equal social and legal rights as men, and one of the main ways to draw attention to their plight was through writing. Women wrote to make a living, to contribute to the literary world and most importantly to change British society and fight for women's rights. Restrictions on voting and property rights, educational opportunities, and employment were issues facing 19th century British women. Many women decided to take up the issues by writing and publishing to make their voices heard and demand equality. As a result, feminism grew out of the frustration women faced with a blatantly unfair and deteriorating social and political situation. Among the most famous female novelists of this period were Charlotte Brontë and George Eliot. Many Victorian women published their works anonymously or under pseudonyms in order to ensure that their works were given the credit they deserved over the works of male authors. Charlotte Brontë was one

of the most prominent novelists of the Victorian era, publishing most of her work under the gender-neutral pen name Currer Bell. In her novels, Brontë created strong female characters with free thinking, intelligence and strong moral character. She wrote for women oppressed by society, including teachers, governesses, and spinsters. Charlotte Brontë was the eldest of the three Brontë sisters who survived to adulthood and whose novels have become classics of English literature.

He wrote during the Victorian era of British literature, which lasted from 1833-1901, and is associated with the reign of Queen Victoria. [2] In this article, I would like to focus on the issues of women and society in the novels of Charlotte Brontë. This article attempts to explore the extent to which Charlotte Brontë succeeded in creating female characters, the role of women and society in her novels, and how successful she was in confronting the traditional Victorian society and dramatizing her life events. problems and describes them in novels and also uses imagination. However, she tries to explain Brontë's goals and the messages she wanted to send in presenting historical images of Victorian women. The ideal Victorian woman's life in Victorian times revolved around her family's domestic sphere and home. Middle-class women were "brought up to be pure and innocent, gentle and without sexual demands, submissive and submissive. A woman had no rights of her own and had to marry and be a servant to her husband. However, several occupations .besides the governor, it was open to educated women who needed the means to support themselves. Women believed that higher education was a waste because they were considered intellectually inferior to men, and moreover, work was believed to make them sick. Women's education included singing, dancing and learning to play the piano, drawing, reading, writing and some arithmetic. influenced by fairy tales. Charlotte continued to write and she longed to be a paid writer like male writers. Margaret (2007) notes that Charlotte once wrote to the English poet Robert Southey for advice wrote Southey's response shocked Charlotte, as it stated: "Literature cannot be the work of a woman's life. The more she is busy with her

duties, the less free time she has, even for success and relaxation. You are not yet called to these duties, and here you are less eager for fame."

She was discouraged by this answer, but she appreciated the advice and stopped writing for a while. However, the years in which he gave up writing greatly influenced his future work. According to Southey and many other members of Victorian society, literature is only the work of human life. The response was not supportive. However, Charlotte Brontë insisted on a challenge until literature became women's business and allowed them to dominate the fiction market. Despite the lack of support from people around the world, she was very motivated and got enough encouragement from her sisters to become a successful writer. [3] As for Robert Southey's response to Charlotte about women's writing, many critics have supported Southey in arguing that literature is the work of men only. One of them is George Lewes. As Reef (2012) notes, George Lewes asks, "These beautiful creatures were not meant to press ink with their little fingers, but to kiss them." George Lewes supports the Victorian view that a woman is an angel in the home. So, he wants to say that instead of inking the hands of these charming creatures (women), they should be kissed. Victorian society was against women in all walks of life. It was male-dominated, and even educated critics were patriarchal in their behavior. Patriarchy was not only social but also literary. Charlotte Brontë, Jane Austen, George Eliot, and many other women writers fought against the oppression of women in a largely male-dominated society. Such novelists were heralds of the feminist movement that flourished in the 20th century. On the other hand, some other male critics and writers in the world of fiction like William Thackeray and Elizabeth Gaskell gave Charlotte Brontë a positive boost and she admired them and appreciated them through her fiction. Smith (1995) confirms that Brontë commands Jane Eyre to appreciate Thackeray: "There is one man in our time whose words do not tickle the ears; they are, in my opinion, before the greats of society. He adds – I am proud to be endorsed by Mr Thackeray as I endorse Mr Thackeray. One good word of such a man is worthy of the praise of ordinary judges." Charlotte Bronte is

very happy to have found a man who can appreciate her works. Thackeray, unlike other critics of the 19th century, praised Charlotte Brontë's works favorably.

Thus she felt that the good word of a man like Thackeray was worthy of praise by ordinary judges. He was disillusioned by George Lewes and Robert Southey that literature was the work of men only. In a letter to Charlotte Brontë's publisher Smith, Thackeray praised *Jane Eyre*, saying, "I was so interested in the novel that I lost a day to read it...Give my respect and thanks to the author of the novel, first English." Charlotte Brontë told her publisher that she was particularly pleased with Thackeray's commentary because she found that Thackeray was able to distinguish the dross from the ore, the real from the fake. In Charlotte Brontë's literary work, *The Weaver* (1883), Brontë as a Victorian writer emphasizes that he rejects the concept of an ideal woman, who has no dignity: "Woman is the priestess of the house and she puts herself in it and its affairs and conditions. His talent and taste were a natural fit for this sacred post. He is most satisfied and useful when the work of the home occupies his mind and heart." Victorian societies had clear boundaries between what men should do and what jobs should be done by women. A man earns money and is supported by his wife, mother, [4] On the other hand, women's duties are to provide for children's education and care, shopping, housekeeping, and maintaining a peaceful and prosperous home. Burstyn (1980) states that the work of a woman in the shelter building: it has a religious and educational value, because by her kindness she inculcates beautiful morals and ethical values so that the woman can be a social protector of the society. It turns out that all the characters, including Brontë's *Jane Eyre*, never followed the traditional Victorian model of life in which women were oppressed by men. why, she removes her characters from the home to give them a kind of autonomy from male domination. He wants to give them more power than those in the house, who are considered "House Angels". He rebels against the "House Angel" routine. This is because it restricts the freedom of the woman who is kept within the bounds of the man and left as the architect of the house. So all the characters of Charlotte Brontë ran away from home to prove

themselves. True, they are another copy of Bronte's life, which also reflects her biography and ideas.

Research and methods

Descriptive analytical method is used in this research work. It describes the hero's biography and the problems he faced along the way and how his characters developed. However, a comparison is made between the new characteristics of the characters presented by Charlotte Bronte and the images, characteristics and roles of real Victorian women.

Analysis and results

It can be seen that Charlotte Brontë deliberately created characters in her novels to deny the traditional views of women inherited from the Victorian era and to deny the attempts to convey her views about women and their rights. Her new ideas and views about women are considered feminist by some scholars. Feminism is a set of social movements, political movements and ideologies with a common goal: to define, establish and achieve political, economic, personal and social equality of the sexes.

Cumber and Sarah stated: Feminism expresses the idea that societies support a male perspective and that women are treated unfairly in these cultures. Efforts for change include challenging gender stereotypes and providing women with equal educational and professional opportunities to men. [7] In the 19th century and in such a patriarchal society (Victorian society), the status of women and their importance in all spheres was neglected. Although England was a powerful and rich country, they faced various difficulties. It is important to study the creative activity and literary world of every writer. The literary world of Charlotte Brontë is unique. Because Charlotte focuses heavily on gender issues in her novels, it is convenient to get a good look at the lives of women in Victoria. And middle-class women's clothing was distinguished from the commercial and worldly by the vagars, a kind of prosperity that accompanied business from the home, which made the main women intellectually superior to earning money, and left them with no commercial

clothing. what for self-possession is purging, basically all women outside the working class, purging no trace of work except in cases of extreme necessity. For middle-class Victorian women, the only viable options were actually marriage, dependence on the family patriarch, or becoming a governess. The latter became Charlotte Brontë's occupation, and although she hated the profession; it also provided a lot of inspiration for his work. [8] Women's thinking and role in society as a whole created a great momentum for Charlotte Brontë, as she herself was a woman who wanted to overcome her support. In this way, Charlotte carries out a kind of revolution, raising accepted literary themes that had never before been explored and was not fully understood at the time. In Victoria, women were expected to rule in private, domestic spheres, while the public sphere belonged to men, although most nineteenth-century English thrones were occupied by women. again, the queen herself did not support women's emancipation and even called the women's suffrage movement in 1840.

Brontë uses female characters to send themselves messages and her own perspective on Victorian conventions of women's conventions in her novel Jane Eyes, she uses her first personal narrative to help readers see the characters and listen to their real problems. is determined. Jane Eyre was published in 1840, women in Victorian societies and every social class were treated as inferior and worse than men and did not have the right to vote or express their opinions. Brontë presents her readers with a Jane character who is strong, passionate and able to express herself and fight for her rights. Her features are completely different from those of real Victorian women who were oppressed by men. It shows many of the things that Jane would do and that Victorian women were not allowed to do. The traditional perception shows women as dependent, weak and dull; Jane is the exact opposite of these characteristics and images. She is a strong and passionate woman who makes a strong impression on readers who first see her as a child at the beginning of the story. At the opening of the story, he had a fight with his cousin. The conversation between Jane and the maid is as follows: — "Miss Eyre, how awful to strike a young

gentleman of your benevolent son! Your young master." - "Master! How is he my boss? Am I a servant?" Readers can learn how strong, simple and passionate Jane is. Through Jane, Charlotte Brontë rebels against the inequality between men and women in the nineteenth century. She portrays this rejection in the resistant behavior of Jane Eyre. Charlotte Brontë is also an author known for her interest in gender issues, particularly women. In her novel *The Professor*, she focuses on the situation of women in Victorian society, where they are completely disadvantaged. She creates a male character, William Crimsworth, to stand up for her because women are not allowed to speak freely and express her feelings and ideas. In addition, gender equality is a major concern of hers. [9] The novel attempts to discuss: William's representation of the female voice, the new womanhood and the new marriage, in addition to the female role in *The Professor*. In *The Professor*, Brontë tended to use the male protagonist, William Crimsworth, as the narrator of the story. Her journey is about achieving financial independence because "I must live, and to live I must have what you call 'needs,' which I can only get by working" (Bronte 59).

Thus, Glenn Heather argues that the professor is a "self-help story." " (Bronte 72) because Bronte says: "True living men had seen their labours, he had never seen him work for a shilling, he had not worked, no sudden turns made him instantly whatever little talent he possessed, he had to swallow in his sweat, lest he should rise to wealth and high rank.' And this idea can only be applied to a male character who has the power of his gender. William is simply a female voice that represents a woman's journey to independence. It is believed that her brother treats her like a servant, not only to achieve financial independence, but also to seek respectable social status and identity. I order ... and there are no questions! You are my servant..." (Bronte, 49). William then said, "I escaped from Big Ben Close without breaking my resolution; without harming my self-respect" (53) and "I felt light and free" [10]. William, the narrator, has a physical disability. She describes herself as saying, "I wasn't that pretty; I had a dark eye, a wider brow - thin, lighter, not so tall" (20) and "I must be a slave". In other words, Bronte uses the word "slave". to express

inferiority by. This is a biological theory that in that era (Victorian era) women are inferior because it is like a woman, only women care about their physical features and beauty, but William thinks about it. That is, his speech expresses a female voice. Characterizing the character with these characteristics gave the reader a sense of expressing the narrator's desires and wishes. As a female narrator, Brontë tells what women suffer and what they want to be. chooses her protagonist for. The writer pretends to be a man to better express her ideas, feelings and interests. Through her protagonist, she, as a feminist writer emphasizes that the patriarchal ideology between men and women is based on their inner and spiritual identity rather than the sexual body that discriminates. According to Sandra Gilbert and Susan Geber, *The Professor* explores the life of a strong-willed woman in a patriarchal society, which *Crushworthy* allegorizes and gives voice to Charlotte Brontë's anger and despair. Writer Brontë shows aggressive individuals against each other in society. Thus, according to Christopher Lane, freedom was manifested as a rejection of society and independence. In addition, Crimsworth did not benefit from his father's status. His antipathy to society is the result of his circumstances. He lives with his uncles, then he is "sent to Eton" (Bronte 11). Her social status and weakness contribute to her femininity. In such a patriarchal society, it denies him the right of inheritance. It is clear that Brontë challenges conventions that equate dominance with masculinity and weakness with femininity.[11]

Research results

The results of the research can be used in conducting research on world literature, literary history and English literature. In the article, the future direction of the science is defined to a certain extent, that is, in the future, research can be carried out on the topics of "Women's role in society" and "Modern literature". The practical importance of the work can be determined by using its conclusion in teaching "World Literature", "History of Literature" and "English Literature" and conducting special courses.

Summary

Charlotte Bronte's works show that her existence reflected her truth and spirit, which was not valued in society. In *Jane Eyre*, Charlotte develops many themes that she previously explored in *The Professor*: education, the search for independence, marriage, gender issues, feelings of loneliness and alienation, family, and more. In her second novel, Charlotte makes better use of placing a female protagonist at the center of the story, allowing her to explore themes in a more personal and relatable way. [12] In this way, Charlotte Brontë was able to portray an ultimately equal marriage with two people finding their way to each other despite all the conflicts and strict traditions of her time. He made this simple scenario more relevant and relatable by applying the moral dilemmas and issues of gender and equality that were central to his time. Throughout her professional career, Charlotte Brontë continued to return to certain themes in her novels. In both *The Professor* and *Jane Eyre*, she explores themes of gender, equality, self-gratification, religion, education, or the search for independence. In her second novel, Brontë was able to explore the theme of gender issues in a more relatable and realistic way, as she placed a female character at the center of the story and thus could better use her emotional experience. was Although the marriage in both novels is based on love and equality, Jane's relationship with Rochester develops throughout the novel and is aimed at achieving equal status from the beginning - the relationship between William Crimsworth and Frances Henry in *The Professor* is mostly until Frances expresses her ambitions and William when they don't object, it's the male protagonist's "responsibility" until they get married. Without her liberal upbringing, the influence of her siblings, and the inspiring environment of wild nature outside her window, Charlotte Brontë would never have achieved such success in the world of literature. Although readers and critics wonder how she, a woman from a village in Yorkshire, could write such fantasy novels. As a woman with a strong desire for independence and ambition, Bronte made these issues central to her novels. Although it is somewhat expected in our time that people should raise awareness of issues related to social issues, this was not the case in Victorian times. It was not a place for women to criticize their position, and it was

not a place for them to do so publicly in the form of literature. However, Brontë was a brave woman who was not afraid to address the "Woman Question" in her work, and she did it so masterfully that her novels still represent female strength and ability. Historical context was an important element in Brontë's development both as a woman and as a writer.

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